

Translation from German to English of: *‘Zur Kenntniss der resorption einfacher, im besonderen stereoisomer zucker im dünndarm’* by Junzo Nagano.

Here we present a translation from German to English of a scientific paper titled ‘On the knowledge of the absorption of simple, in particular stereoisomeric sugars in the small intestine’ published in the journal Pflugers Arch. 90:389–404 in 1902 [1]. We provide the translation because this work represents an important contribution to the historical scientific record focusing on cell membrane function. We have included a brief foreword highlighting some of the scientific and historical context of the work.

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Introduction: foreword to the translation

Cells are contained within a surface layer called the cell membrane which is made up of a phospholipid bilayer. Some cellular forms possess two cell membrane bilayers and in some lineages the membrane is combined with a cell wall. In combination, this structure is referred to as the cell envelope. Understanding cell membrane function, and how compounds move across this cellular structure, is a major subject in biology. Firstly, this function determines how cells maintain physiological states, transform energy (for example, through electron transport chains), take up nutrients, disperse and receive chemical messages, and dispose of waste products. Secondly, the function of cell membranes can determine how drugs (e.g., antibiotics) enter the cell during treatment, and how cells interact physically with their environment and other cells. Thirdly, the function of this structure is an important theme in evolutionary biology as membrane function determines how cells can colonise variant niches and compete with other cells [2, 3]. Furthermore, understanding how this biological structure functions is important for understanding how the earliest cellular forms (protocells) evolved [4-7].

The scientific field of membrane biology has a long history with many important moments of discovery (reviewed here [8-10]). Cell membranes have been known to be semi-permeable barriers since the late 18th century (see [8, 11]), functioning to maintain cellular integrity but allowing some compounds to cross the membrane whilst excluding others. The

paper translated here, was an important addition to this field of research [8] by demonstrating that cell membranes have different permeability characteristics for different sugar compounds. Our interest in this work stems from the author's aim to compare how different compounds, chiefly six and five carbon sugars, are absorbed across intestinal membranes. Although direct experimental comparisons are limited within this paper, largely by the experimental systems used and type of pure sugar compounds available at the time, the work demonstrates that compounds with different structures (i.e., numbers of carbons) have different uptake characteristics. Given the experimental conditions reported, such traits are likely to be determined by the type and number of transporter proteins found in the cell membranes (as demonstrated for yeast here [3]).

Early work directly proposing that metabolites enter the cell by processes other than diffusion came some thirty years after this paper [8, 12, 13]. Indeed, it was not until the 1970's that the fluid mosaic hypothesis was put forward. This hypothesis outlined how the cell membrane is made up of lipids, proteins, and carbohydrates [14]. The paper translated here predates this understanding by over 65 years. As such the author would not have been aware that transportation of compounds across membranes is largely determined by proteins embedded within the membrane. Much of the physiological effect discussed in this paper would therefore be a product of the function of different membrane transporter proteins and the relative number of these proteins present in and across the membrane. The diversity, substrate range, substrate affinity, and the abundance of variant transporter proteins (rather than just the semi-permeability of the membrane itself) drive differing rates of sugar uptake.

Interestingly, part of the work reported includes a comparison of how different stereochemical forms (stereoisomers or enantiomers) cross the intestinal membrane. Although no direct comparisons of L- and D- stereoisomers of the same compound are included, limiting the utility of the comparisons made. It is likely this limitation stems from the scant availability of purified stereoisomers of certain sugar compounds during this period of history. In the preceding years, there have been very few studies which have compared how different stereoisomers cross membrane structures, with only a single study to our knowledge comparing L- and D- stereoisomers of the five carbon sugar xylose in 2005 [7], over 100 years later.

Scientific focus on sugar production and the metabolism of sugars was a growing field in Germany in the late 1800s and early 1900s, where this research was conducted and the

subsequent paper published [1]. This growing industry was derived from Andreas Sigismund Marggraf's discovery of sugar in beet (*Beta vulgaris*) and his development of a methodology for extraction of this sugar using alcohol [15]. In 1783, Franz Karl Achard devised an economically scalable industrial process for sugar extraction from beets [16]. Following these discoveries, sugar derived from beet rose from 14 per cent of gross annual global sugar production in 1853 to 65 per cent in 1900, reaching 8,908,00 tons at the beginning of the 1st World War [17]. In 1913, Germany was the leading global producer of sugar from sugar beet and produced ~2,304,000 tons annually (26% of global output). This represented the greatest level of production per acre, 35% higher production per acre than France [17], the second highest global producer of sugar from sugar beet. At the height of this agricultural-industrial production over 100,000 people (mostly women and children) were employed in the sugar beet industry in Germany [17]. Germany's success in this industry was in part due to scientific research leading to improved yields. This progress meant that sugar recovery from beet changed from 0.45 kg (1 pound) of sugar from 8.1 kg of beets to 0.45 kg of sugar recovered from 2.7 kg of beets [17]. This represents a nearly four-fold improvement in the efficiency of this industrial process. The paper translated here is one example of the scientific and industrial focus, in Germany in the early 1900s, on sugar and its metabolism.

Here we provide a translation of this paper from German to English. We have provided a few translation notes indicated in square brackets throughout the manuscript regarding choice of alternative terminology or where we have altered the formatting of the tables from the original paper. We have translated this paper to enable wider access to this work and to facilitate discussion of research assessing how different stereoisomers cross membranes.

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(From the chemical laboratory of the physiological institute in Breslau.)

**On the knowledge of the absorption of simple, in particular stereoisomeric
sugars in the small intestine.**

by

Junzo Nagano.

(With 1 line drawing.)

On the basis of his experiments on the absorption of saline solutions and blood serum, R. Heidenhain¹ famously came to the view that the laws of osmosis are insufficient in explaining absorption in the intestine, that one is instead compelled to assume special driving forces which are located in the cells of the intestinal mucosa.

Ever since Heidenhain's work, a number of studies have appeared which have opened up new perspectives on the assessment of "physical factors" of absorption. Reference should be made here to the observations of Max Oker-Blom,² which show the significance for an understanding of the absorption process of those ideas that we have of the nature of the absorbing membrane; and one should also note the work of R. Höber³ in which attention is directed to the physico-chemical properties of the solution to be absorbed. He states that the speed with which various salts are absorbed in the small intestine is in proportion to their rate of diffusion.

Höber also did a number of experiments on the absorption of various sugars. "Glucose [a monosaccharide] is absorbed much more slowly than sodium chloride but quite considerably faster than magnesium sulfate; galactose, which is isomeric to glucose [also a monosaccharide], is absorbed about as quickly as glucose and the cane sugar disaccharides and lactose [also a disaccharide], more slowly than both the monoses [monosaccharides]."

According to Höber, the rate of diffusion is likewise important for the absorption of sugars; as glucose, which diffuses more slowly than sucrose, also takes longer to be absorbed. The lower absorption rate of glucose observed by him as compared to sodium chloride is also consistent with this view. But as Hüber points out, there is also

¹ This archive, vol. 56, p. 629 (1894).

² This archive, vol. 85, p. 543 (1901).

³ This archive, vol. 74, p. 246 (1899).

a second factor to consider: the concentration gradient. The faster the sugar disappears from the intestinal wall, the greater the difference between the solution's concentration in the intestine and the content of absorbed substance in the intestinal wall, the faster will be the diffusion into the intestinal wall.

The discharge of sugar from the intestinal wall can be influenced by various circumstances, including the ease with which the cells of the intestinal mucosa absorb and process the sugar.

However, the role played by the intestinal mucosa in the absorption of sugars in comparison to the diffusion rates cannot yet be determined. But a clue to its assessment could be gained by comparing the absorption of different simple sugars. It can be assumed that the diffusion rates of these sugars do not differ greatly, but it is known that their behavior is very different from the processes in living cells.

We know that sugars with three, six and nine carbon atoms are fermentable, whereas those with five and seven are not, and that pentoses are much more difficult to burn [respire] in the organism than hexoses. Furthermore, within the same group, the stereoisomeric sugars would also have to be examined, firstly those in which the shape of the molecule behaves like an image and mirror image, i.e. the D- and L-series [enantiomer notations changed to capitals as is the modern convention]. Only the former are capable of fermentation [probably referring to use for respiration and energy transformation], and the two series also show differences in the metabolism of animals, as can be seen from the behavior of arabinoses, which were examined in E. Salkowski's laboratory by C. Neuberg and J. Wohlgemuth.⁴ The influence of the other configurations should also be ascertained. It is known, for example, that the assimilation limits of the various hexoses⁵ in the animal organism are not the same. To cite an example, as seen in experiments done by G. Rosenfeld,⁶ the dextrose in the organism was completely burned up, whereas 16 percent of the galactose and 20 percent of the mannose was excreted unchanged in the urine when administered in equal amounts. An analogous difference appears to exist between xylose and arabinose in the case of pentoses.

⁴ Ber. d. deutsch. chem. Ges., vol. 34, pp. 1745 (1901).

⁵ See F. Hofmeister, Arch. F. exp. Path., vol. 25, p. 240 (1889).

⁶ Centralbl. f. innere Med. (1900) no. 7.

How do these different simple sugars behave when they are absorbed in the intestine?

There is only one difficulty in a full-scale investigation of this kind, namely the nature of the sugars, especially in the requisite quantities.

For the time being we must limit ourselves to carrying out experiments with the most easily accessible sugars. Of the aldohexoses, these are D-glucose, D-galactose and D-mannose; of the ketoses, D-fructose; of the aldopentoses, L-arabinose and L-xylose.

Before I describe my experiments, which I carried out at the suggestion and with the support of Prof. F. Röhmman, I will not fail to mention that, in addition to Höber, E. Hédon⁷ has also published a series of experiments that are pertinent here. Hédon filled the intestinal loops of rabbits with equal amounts of a sugar solution that was roughly isotonic with the blood serum and determined the amount of sugar still present in the intestine after two hours. He found that glucose and galactose were better absorbed than arabinose and far better than raffinose.

Method of Investigation.

As is well known, absorption experiments in the intestine can be carried out in two ways. The liquid to be examined can be introduced into ligated intestinal loops and the intestinal contents examined after a certain time; or the experiments can be carried out on dogs with Vella intestinal fistulas. Both methods have their advantages, both have their disadvantages.⁸ The former requires a large amount of animal material; the anesthesia, the opening of the abdominal cavity, the manipulations with the loop can influence the absorption in an uncontrollable way. Furthermore, because of the varying contraction of the intestine, it seems to me impossible during the operation to determine, with requisite accuracy, the length of the piece of intestine in which the absorption is to take place. In Vella fistulas the loop sees usage only after it has been deprived of its normal function for a certain time. The intestinal mucosa of the loop can change over time, especially as sooner or later a "catarrhal state" of the mucosa usually sets in, which manifests itself in a slight decrease in absorption capacity and a tendency to hyper-secretion. However, the dangers posed by this can be avoided. If it

⁷ Compt. Rend. de la Soc. De Biol., vol. 52, pp. 29, 41, 87 (1900).

⁸ See Waymouth Reid, The Journ. of Physiology, vol. 19, p. 240 (1895).

is a question of comparing solutions that do not have an irritant effect per se, it is only necessary to change the order of the tests accordingly in order to obtain comparable results. The advantage of being able to perform the experiments on the same animal without anesthesia and always on the same intestinal loop under the same conditions seemed so great that only dogs with Vella intestinal fistulas were used for the following experiments.

Dog I, operated on 22 April, killed on 29 July 1901. Intestinal suture 230 cm from the pylorus, 7 cm from the cecum. Length of the surgically removed [excised] piece of intestine 22 cm. -- Body weight: on 9 May 1901, 12.05 kg; 17 May, 13.5 kg; 12 June, 14 kg; 28 July, 15.3 kg.

Dog II, operated on 21 May, killed on 28 June 1901 due to intestinal prolapse. 20 cm from the pylorus, 126 cm from the cecum. Length of the surgically removed [excised] piece of intestine 24 cm. -- Body weight: On 5 June, 14.3 kg; 26 June, 15.3 kg.

Dog III, operated on 2 July, killed on 30 July 1901, suture 63.5 cm from the pylorus, 160 cm from the cecum. Length of the surgically removed [excised] piece of intestine 18 cm. -- Body weight: On 10 July 1901, 12.2 kg; 28 July, 12.0 kg.

Dog IV, suture site 50 cm from the pylorus, 210 cm from the cecum. Length of surgically removed [excised] piece intestinal section 27 cm.

All the experiments carried out on these dogs were done as follows.

The anterior fistula opening was closed with a rubber balloon that could be inflated with water. A tampon cannula was inserted into the posterior fistula opening. This consisted of a metal tube 14 cm long and 4-5 mm in diameter; at *a* and *b* two strips about 1 mm thick and 5 mm wide with grooves were soldered on, onto which was tied a thin cylindrical piece of rubber (cut from the finger of a glove). Going through *b* is a thin tube that can be closed at its end by a small spigot. At *d* a syringe filled with water is attached by means of a piece of rubber tubing, the water is forced between the cannula and the rubber bladder and the spigot is closed. A short rubber tube is pulled over the end *c* of the cannula, which can be closed with a stopcock. Connect it through a glass tube to a longer piece of rubber tubing that leads to a burette, fill the burette and tubing with the liquid that is to be absorbed, and with the same

dog always allow the same amount of liquid to flow into the fistula. This leaves 0.5-1 cc in the cannula and the tube in a kind of dead space. The closure is perfect; the few drops that fall from the fistula opening during the experiment arise from intestinal fluids, which is secreted by the mucous membrane on the outside of the closure pieces under the influence of the pressure exerted by them.

During the entire experiment the dog stood quietly in a suitable framework. After each test it was fed the same food (200 g of meat and 1 - 2 dog biscuits). All the experiments were thus carried out with the dog having not eaten anything before surgery.

After a certain time -- generally after one hour -- the liquid was drained and measured. In all experiments after 7 May 1901 the fistula was rinsed out with 0.5 percent saline solution at end of the experiment. The alkalinity was determined in the effluent by adding 1/10 normal sulphuric acid (1 ccm = 4.0 mg Na₂CO₃) from a burette until the blue coloration of red lacmoid paper disappeared. If the neutralized liquid is heated to a boil, the protein coagulates and can be removed by filtration. The latter is achieved more quickly and safely if, after neutralization, a certain amount of sodium acetate and iron(III) chloride is added to the liquid and then heated to a boil.

In the liquid with proteins removed, the sugar was determined by titration with Mercury solution after Knapp. The titer was determined empirically for each sugar.

Experiments.

A. Absorption of hexoses

1. D-Glucose

Pure crystallized glucose from S. A. F. Kahlbaum in Berlin was used.

Experiments on Dog I.

	Date 1901								
	7 May	8 May	10 May	17 May	9 May	11 July	19 July	10 July	
Glucose solution	1%	2%	5%	5%	6%	7.5%	5%	6%	7.5%
Introduced in ccm	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Effluent in ccm	nothing	nothing	nothing	nothing	10	17	9.5	17	14.5
Alkalinity ⁹	--	--	--	--	0.9	2.35	2.6	7.2	6.9
Glucose,									
introduced in g	0.3	0.6	1.5	1.5	1.8	2.25	1.5	1.8	2.25
effluent in g	--	--	--	--	0.434	0.686	0.41	0.541	1.14
Absorbed in g	--	--	--	--	1.36	1.56	1.09	1.26	1.11
Absorbed	--	--	--	--	75.8%	69%	73%	70%	50%
Water, absorbed	--	--	--	--	66%	43%	71%	43%	18%

The absorption of glucose and water was lower in the July experiments than those in May; the secretion of alkali was also considerably increased, both of which were a sign that the intestinal loop was no longer in a completely normal state.

Experiments on Dog III.

	Date 1901		
	20 July	22 July	19 July

⁹ In cubic centimeters, alkalinity means 1/10 normal sulphuric acid. The secretion of intestinal fluids was not taken into account when calculating the water retention.

Glucose solution	5%	5%	6%
Introduced in ccm	30	30	30
Effluent in ccm	14.5	15.0	18.0
Alkalinity	1.35	1.1	1.5
Glucose, introduced in g	1.5	1.5	1.8
Glucose, effluent in g	0.526	0.554	0.820
Glucose, absorbed in g	0.974	0.946	0.980
Glucose, absorbed in g [typo?]	65%	63%	54.4%
Water, absorbed	51%	50%	40.0%

In these experiments carried out on Dog III, less glucose was absorbed than in Dog I. The reason, as the section showed, was only that the intestinal loop was shorter than that of Dog I, namely 18 cm as compared to 22 cm. A comparison of absorption in the upper and lower parts of the intestine is not possible on the basis of these experiments. Noteworthy is the low alkalinity in the upper part of the intestine, which also does not increase as the percentage of sugar and water absorption decreases with increasing concentration of the sugar solution.

2. D-Galactose.

Galactose was obtained from lactose by inversion with hydrochloric acid. Its purity was controlled by determining its rotary power. It amounted to $[\alpha]_{D/20} + 79.3$ degrees. [D/20: Specific optical rotatory power refers to the angle of rotation (which varies from one sugar to the next), measured at 20°C using a polarimeter with a 1-dm path, produced by a solution containing 1 g/mL of sugar at the characteristic spectral line of sodium, known as the D line. It is expressed by $[\alpha]_D^{20}$]

Experiments on Dog I.

Of a 2 and 5% galactose solution, 30 ccm were completely absorbed.

13 May 1901. 30 ccm of a 7.5% galactose solution was introduced into the intestinal loop. The effluent was 7 ccm with an alkalinity of 1.2. The effluent contained 0.37 g galactose. 83.5% galactose and 76% water was absorbed.

Experiments on Dog II.

Date 1901		
	12 June	17 June
Galactose solution	7.5%	10%
Introduced	30 ccm	30 ccm
Effluent	4.0 ccm	19 ccm
Alkalinity	0.5	2.6
Galactose, introduced	2.25 g	3.00 g
Galactose, effluent	0.104 g	0.60 g
Galactose, absorbed	2.14 g	2.40 g
Galactose, absorbed	95%	80%
Water, absorbed	86%	37%

Experiments on Dog III.

24 July 1901. The intestinal loop was filled with 30 ccm of a 7.5% galactose solution, i.e. 2.25 g galactose.

The effluent was 24 ccm with an alkalinity of 2.0. The effluent contained 1.12 g galactose. Absorbed 1.13 g, i.e. 50% galactose and 20% water.

3. D-Mannose.

We received D-mannose in the form of a white crystalline preparation through the kindness of Prof. Herzfeld, to whom we owe many thanks. The rotary power was determined in circa 5% solution to $[\alpha]_{D/20} = + 13.6$ degrees.

Experiments on Dog I.

Date 1901				
	22 May	21 May	14 May	19 May
Mannose solution	1%	2.5%	5%	5%
Introduced in ccm	30	30	30	30
Effluent in ccm	nothing	7	15	17.5
Alkalinity	--	0.8	2.4	2.3
Mannose, introduced in g	0.30	0.75	1.50	1.50

Mannose, effluent in g	--	0.217	0.605	0.660
Mannose, absorbed in g	--	0.53	0.895	0.840
Mannose, absorbed	--	70%	59%	56%
Water, absorbed	--	75%	50%	41%

4. D-Fructose.

Kahlbaum's crystalline fructose was used. Determining its rotary power in c. 6 % solution $[\alpha]_{D/20}$ -- 95.24 degrees.

Experiments on Dog I.

Date 1901				
	18 May	20 May	23 May	
Fructose	2.5%	5%	7.5%	
Introduced in ccm	30	30	30	
Effluent	nothing	4.5	19.0	
Alkalinity	--	1.0	1.6	
Fructose, introduced in g	0.75	1.5	2.25	
Fructose, effluent in g	--	0.178	0.893	
Fructose, absorbed	--	1.32	1.36	
Fructose, absorbed	--	88%	60%	
Water, absorbed	--	85%	37%	

B. Absorption of Pentoses.

The experiments were carried out with L-xylose and L-arabinose. The former was prepared in accordance with Tollens¹⁰ from wheat straw, the latter in accordance with Kiliani¹¹ from cherry gum. Both preparations had been repeatedly recrystallized from alcohol.

Experiments on Dog I.

Date 1901

¹⁰ Annalen d. Chem., vol. 271, p. 40.

¹¹ Ber. d. deutsch. Chem. Ges., vol. 19, p. 3029.

	25 July	26 July	27 July
	Xylose	Xylose	Arabinose
Sugar solution	0.5%	2%	2%
Introduced in ccm	30	30	30
Effluent in ccm	2	4.5	10
Alkalinity	1.35	3.1	6.1
Sugar, introduced in g	0.15	0.60	0.60
Sugar, effluent in g	Traces	0.156	0.326
Sugar, absorbed in g	--	0.444	0.274
Sugar, absorbed	--	74.8%	45.8%
Water, absorbed	--	85%	66%

Experiments on Dog III.

Date 1901		
	29 July	28 July
	Xylose	Arabinose
Sugar solution	2%	2%
Introduced in ccm	30	30
Effluent in ccm	11	17
Alkalinity	1.3	1.3
Sugar, introduced in g	0.600	0.600
Sugar, effluent in g	0.200	0.357
Sugar, absorbed in g	0.400	0.243
Sugar, absorbed	66%	40%
Water, absorbed	63%	43%

Findings.

From the experiments reported here it is possible to determine the speed at which the solutions of simple sugars are absorbed in the intestine:

The rate of absorption of stereoisomeric sugars is various.

This can be seen in both the experiments with hexoses and with pentoses.

Experiments on Dog I.

D-Galactose.

2 - 5% solution completely absorbed
 7.5% solution 83% absorbed

D-Mannose.

1% solution completely absorbed
 2.5% solution 71% absorbed
 5% solution 56 - 59% absorbed

D-Glucose.

1 - 5% solution completely absorbed
 6% solution 75% absorbed
 7.5% solution 69% absorbed

D-Fructose.

2.5% solution completely absorbed
 5% solution 88% absorbed
 7.5% solution 60% absorbed

As can be seen, D-galactose is absorbed somewhat better than D-glucose and D-glucose much better than D-mannose from solutions of equal concentration, i.e. in this case equimolecular ones.

The absorption of D-fructose, which as ketosis cannot be equated with these three sugars, is somewhat worse than that of D-glucose, but better than that of mannose.

Among the stereoisomeric pentoses, the absorption of xylose is better than that of arabinose.

Of 2% L-xylose, 74.8% was absorbed in Dog I and 66% in Dog II

Of 2% L-arabinose, 45.8% was absorbed in Dog I and 40% in Dog II.

At the same time, a comparison of the pentoses and hexoses shows that the sugars with five carbon atoms are absorbed more slowly in the intestine than those with six carbon atoms.

The speed of water absorption of the various sugar solutions of identical concentration shows similar differences as the absorption of sugars.

Introduced into the Intestine	Absorbed	Absorbed
	Sugar	Water
	%	%
7.5% galactose	83	76
7.5% glucose	69	43
5% glucose	completely	completely
5% mannose	56 - 59	41 - 50

2% xyclose	74.8	85
2% arabinose	45.8	66

This would essentially answer, as far as possible from the experiments reported, the initial question as to the behavior of various simple sugars in the intestine.

But these experiments also revealed certain phenomena that are not without interest for the understanding of intestinal absorption.

With the same sugar, the absorption of water decreases with the concentration of the sugar solution introduced into the intestine.

Dog I.

Introduced into the intestine		Water absorbed %
D-Glucose	6%	66
	<u>7.5%</u>	<u>43</u>
	5%	71
	6%	43
	7%	18
D-Mannose	2.5%	75
	5%	50 - 41
D-Fructose	5%	85
	7.5%	37

Dog III.

Introduced into the intestine		Water absorbed %
D-Glucose	5%	50 - 51
	6%	40

Dog II.

Introduced into the intestine		Water absorbed %
D-Galactose	7.5%	86
	10%	37

The increase of osmotic tension therefore delays the exit of water from the intestine. As a hygroscopic force it counteracts those forces which endeavor to bring about the absorption of water.

For sugar, the increase in concentration in the intestine must, within certain limits, create more favorable conditions for absorption by increasing the gradient. Such an influence is also present, as the following figures show.

Dog I.

	Glucose	Mannose	Fructose
Introduced into the intestine	6% 7.5%	2.5% 5%	5% 7.5%
absorbed in g	1.36 1.56	0.53 0.86	1.32 1.36

Dog II.

	Galactose
Introduced into the intestine	7.5% 10%
absorbed in g	2.14 2.40

Dog III.

[order of these tables has been changed for accessibility]

	Glucose
Introduced into the intestine	5% 6%
absorbed in g	0.96 0.98

To compare the rate of absorption of water with that of sugar, the percentage of sugar absorbed can be divided by that of water; the figures obtained for this ratio are shown in the following table.

Ratio of the Absorption of Sugar to Water.

[order of these tables has been changed for accessibility]

Dog I.

D-Galactose	7.5%	1.1
D-Glucose	7.5%	1.6

	6%	1.15
D-Fructose	7.5%	1.62
	5%	1.04
D-Mannose	5%	1.18 and 1.36
	2%	0.95
L-Xylose	2%	0.88
L-Arabinose	2%	0.69

Dog II.

D-Galactose	10%	2.16
	7.5%	1.14

Dog III.

D-Galactose	7.5%	2.50
D-Glucose	6%	1.35
	5%	1.26 and 1.27
L-Xylose	2%	1.04
L-Arabinose	2%	0.93

This indicates that in Dog I the sugar is absorbed faster than the water from sugar solutions whose osmotic tension is higher than that of the blood, i.e. higher than about 4.4%; in solutions of lower tension, the water is absorbed faster than the sugar. In Dog III the corresponding quotients are somewhat greater. Here the sugar from hypertonic solutions at the same concentration decreases more rapidly than in Dog I.

Another expression for the same phenomenon is obtained if, using data from the experiments reported here, one calculates the sugar concentration that the solution of the "absorption residue" contained in the intestine had at the end of the absorption test.

Dog I.

	Absorbed Solution	Absorption Residue
Galactose	7.5%	5.3%
Glucose	6%	4.3%

	7.5%	4.0%
	5%	4.3%
	6%	3.1%
	7.5%	4.1%
Mannose	2.5%	3.1%
	5%	4.0%
	5%	3.9%
Fructose	5%	3.9%
	7.5%	4.7%
Xylose	2%	3.4%
Arabinose	2%	3.2%

Dog III.

	Absorbed Solution	Absorption Residue
Galactose	7.5%	4.2%
Glucose	5%	3.6%
	5%	3.7%
	6%	4.5%
Xylose	2%	1.8%
Arabinose	2%	2.1%

Dog II.

	Absorbed Solution	Absorption Residue
Galactose	10%	3.2%

If a hypertonic solution is introduced into the intestine, the concentration in Dog I drops to about 4%, if one disregards the perhaps not quite correct figure of 3.1%.

On the other hand, the concentration of hypotonic solutions increases. The concentration of the 2.5 % mannose solution rises to 3.1%, that of the 2% xylose solution to 3.4%, and that of the 2% arabinose solution to 3.2%.

Similar observations were made for glucose by O. Cohnheim¹² and partly also by Hédon¹³ and Albertoni.¹⁴ They correspond to the results that Heidenhain and Gumilewski also obtained for the absorption of saline solutions.

If one compares the experiments on Dog I with those on Dog II and Dog III, one finds that when the same sugar solution is absorbed, the solution not yet absorbed in the intestine of the latter contains less sugar than in the former. The solutions of glycose and galactose sink to 3.6%, the 2% solutions of arabinose and xylose are absorbed without any change in concentration, i.e. in the upper part of the intestine the sugar is absorbed proportionally faster than the water, in the lower part the water is absorbed proportionally faster than the sugar.

A few remarks should also be made about the alkalinity that the sugar solutions assume some time after they have abided in the intestine. The figures for this can be found in the following table.

Alkalinity.

Solution	0.5%	2%	3%	5%	6%	7.5%	10%	
Glucose	--	--	--	--	0.9	2.35	--	Dog I
	--	--	--	[2.6]	[7.2]	[6.9] ¹⁵	--	Dog I
	--	--	--	1.35	1.5	--	--	Dog III
	--	--	--	1.1	--	--	--	Dog III
Galactose	--	--	--	--	--	1.2	--	Dog I
	--	--	--	--	--	0.6	2.5	Dog II
	--	--	--	--	--	2.0	--	Dog III
Mannose	--	0.8	--	2.4	--	--	--	Dog I
	--	--	--	2.3	--	--	--	Dog I
Fructose	--	--	--	1.0	--	1.6	--	Dog I
Xylose	1.35	3.1	--	--	--	--	--	Dog I
	--	1.3	--	--	--	--	--	Dog III
Arabinose	--	6.1	--	--	--	--	--	Dog I
	--	1.3	--	--	--	--	--	Dog III

¹² Zeitschr. F. Biol., vol. 36 (18) p. 129.

¹³ Op. cit.

¹⁴ Reale academia di Bologna (1901).

¹⁵ The numbers in brackets stem from the already catarrhal loop.

The amount of alkali secreted by 18-22 cm long intestinal loops during absorption of 0.5 to 10% sugar solutions varied between 4.5 and 35 mg Na₂CO₃.

With the absorption of a 5% mannose solution it was greater than with the absorption of an equally concentrated solution of glucose and galactose, even more so with a 2% xylose or even arabinose solution.

With the same sugar, it increased with the concentration of the added solution. (see the following table.)

Experiments on Dog I.

	Absorbed from 30 ccm of water	Alkali secreted by the intestinal wall
7.5% Galactose	76%	1.2
6% d-Glucose	66%	0.9
7.5% d-Glucose	43%	2.35
2.5% d-Mannose	75%	0.8
5% d-Mannose	50 and 41%	2.4 and 2.3
5% d-Fructose	85%	1.0
7.5% d-Fructose	37%	1.6
2% l-Xylose	85%	3.1
2% l-Arabinose	66%	6.1

When evaluating the findings to which the reported experiments lead, it must first be noted that the diffusion rates of the sugars used in the experiments have not yet been determined. It is therefore also impossible to say whether the observed differences in the absorption rates of the sugars are related to the diffusion rates or not.

It could be attributed to a difference in the gradient that pentoses are absorbed more slowly than hexoses, because, as already mentioned, the latter are also assimilated more slowly and imperfectly than those in the organism. The slower absorption of mannose can also be explained by slower assimilation [here assimilated probably refers to 'utilised for metabolism'].

The situation is different with galactose. Its absorption is just as good, indeed apparently somewhat better even than that of glucose, but its assimilation is

considerably worse. If one wishes to adhere to a physical explanation, it must be borne in mind that the nature of the absorbing membrane cannot be indifferent to the rate of absorption. After all, it is possible that it would be easier for sugar molecules of a certain shape and size (galactose) to pass through than for others (glucose).

Be that as it may, there is a different rate of absorption for different simple sugars, in particular the absorption rate of stereoisomeric sugars, i.e. sugars whose molecule has a different shape but with the same number of atoms and the same type of bonding.